

Research Article

**A Cross-Sectional Descriptive Study on Incidence of Respiratory Insufficiency
in Acute onset of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease**

**¹Ammar Raza Bajwa, ²Nadia Saleem, ³Saba Ahmad
and ⁴Hafiz Muhammad Rizwan Ali**

¹Medical Officer Basic Health Unit, Jodhaywali Tehsil and District Sialkot

²Ex House Officer Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi

³Women Medical Officer Children Hospital and Institute of child Health, Multan

⁴Medical Officer BHU ludaywala Sargodha

ABSTRACT

Background: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute exacerbation is an important health burden. It is accompanied by hypoxia, hypercapnia and acidosis which cause vital functions to deteriorate in the body

Objective: To determine the frequency of respiratory insufficiency in patients of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute exacerbation.

Study Design: It is a descriptive study of cross sectional.

Duration and Setting: Study Conducted for the period of One year from February 2014 to January 2015 in Pulmonology Department Jinnah post Graduate Medical Centre, Karachi.

Subjects and Methods: The total number of patients included in the study was 383 and acute COPD exacerbation was present. Arterial blood sample was immediately collected at presentation, partial pressures of carbon dioxide, oxygen, pH and HCO₃ were analyzed using an arterial blood gas analyzer and analyzed with Social Sciences Statistical Package having 10.0 version.

Results: The number of patients was 383 in total from which 257 (67,10%) male and 126 (32,90%) female. The mean age was 59.3 years + SD 10.76. Respiratory failure was observed in acute exacerbation of COPD, including 136 men (35.51%), 90 men (23.50%) and 46 women (12.01%). The maximum number of patients with respiratory insufficiency was 67 (17.49%) in the age group of 51-60 and the minimum number was recorded as 15 (3.91%) in the 71-80 age group.

Conclusion: Acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is the most common cause of Respiratory failure in patients of tertiary care hospitals should be well equipped for the treatment of these patient.

Keywords: COPD, Acute onset of COPD, SOB.

INTRODUCTION

COPD is a disease with slow progression characterized clinically by a breathlessness obstruction, cough, and / or sputum constant airflow or partially reversible change in basal C patient beyond normal value. FEV / FVC 7.8. (mandatory capacity rate) less than 1 daily variation. Clinical results of 70%. COPD prevalence all over the world auto-limited disease 3.4 9% of COPD ranges between 10% and 10% in

adults who are 40 years of age Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) attacks contribute significant morbidity, mortality and health costs associated with significant affection.acceleration [1].

Acute exacerbation of COPD is characterized by a change on the basis of dyspnea, cough and / or sputum patient line beyond normal daily variation. The clinical consequences of COPD exacerbation

range from a self-limiting disease to a failure of a progressive respiratory disease. Arterial gas analysis revealed respiratory failure in 46.5% of the patients [2, 3]. Acute exacerbations of chronic pulmonary obstruction were abolished in acute exacerbation of COPD in a study in China. when an arterial oxygen pressure (PaO₂) of 60 mmHg and / 45 mm of Hg, carbon dioxide (PaCO₂) lower than the elevated blood pressure is Respiratory failure . respiratory failure in hospital treatment An effective treatment for respiratory failure in COPD-exacerbated patients Oxygen, bronchodilators, glucocorticosteroids, antibiotics and / or ventilation, including non-invasive ventilation or invasive non-invasive ventilation, controlled results Good results under control [4, 5]. The outcome of respiratory insufficiency, factors and available treatment options. available data are available in a limited number of centers in Pakistan that will be organized in hospitals that support critical patients if you want to reduce the high mortality (28%) associated with afección, including adequate non-invasive ventilation. Internationally, according to the frequency of respiratory insufficiency, 18, but not in local regulation or in Karachi. We performed this study to determine the frequency of respiratory failure in patients who present with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute exacerbation of disease in our configuration. The results of this study will help determine the magnitude of the problem that will guide us to establish recommendations for the health facilities required for the management of these critical patients, depending on the magnitude of the problem at our hospital [6, 7, 8].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study of descriptive method was performed in the pulmonology section of Jinnah's pulmonology department from February 2014 to January 2015. Karachi recruited 383 patients with acute COPD exacerbation with a non-probability sampling. Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; (counting more than 25 breaths per minute), as measured by

the previous record spirometry (at least 80% predicted FEV₁ and FEV₁ / FVC at least 70%), as demonstrated by patient COPD with a minute of stopwatch (measured by sputum collection and measured as a glass, 30 mL displacement chamber made for 12 hours) and sputum pus is performed using a microscope in a medical lab at low sputum area, as measured by sputum microscopy for at least the last two days of breathing (increase in pus) . Patients with respiratory insufficiency have O₂ concentration (PaO₂) less than 60 mm of Hg and / or CO₂ arterial tension more than 45 mmHg measured by analyzing the arterial blood sample using the blood gas analyzer available at the hospital. All women and men who were diagnosed with acute exacerbation of CO for 40 years in the pulmonology department of JPMC, Karachi Peshawar were included in the study. Acceptance criteria were severe acute asthma, bronchogenic carcinoma, cardiac arrhythmia, left ventricular failure, pulmonary edema and pneumothorax with COPD; o Patients with severe pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, acute respiratory distress syndrome, respiratory failure associated with kyphoscoliosis.

Approval was taken from the patient's ethics committee. Patients were referred to the Department of Pulmonology at the Jinnah post Graduate medical centre, Karachi with emergency or OPD. Informed consent was obtained from all patients about possible risks and benefits. Demographic characteristics were recorded after the clinical history and physical examination documents were poured out. Using an aseptic technique, a 3 ml blood sample was immediately collected at the time of presentation from the radiation artery. A 5 ml single-use syringe was used to sterilize heparinized with 0.5 ml heparin to prevent blood clotting. The sample was immediately analyzed (AVL Compact 2 Radiometer, Denmark) to detect the partial pressure of carbon dioxide and oxygen using a gas analyzer in arterial blood. Confounding variables were checked by fully applying exclusion criteria. The sample was analyzed 10 minutes after collection at room temperature. Care was taken to

avoid venous blood samples using standard technique. A blood sample was taken before the patient started the oxygenation. The study variables included age, gender, respiratory failure, oxygen partial pressure (PaCO₂) partial carbon dioxide, blood pH in arterial and bicarbonate levels. The data were entered using SPSS version 10.00.

RESULTS

The total number of patients was 383 with acute exacerbation of COPD. There were 257 men (67.10%) and 126 women (32.90%). The ratio of male to female was 2.03: 1. The average age of the male patients was 57.3yrs ± 10.3 SD and the women were 62.1 ± 11.2 SD and the overall mean age was 59.3 years ± 10.76 DS. The number of

patients with respiratory failure in acute COPD exacerbation was 136 (35.51%); 90 of them (23.50%) were male and 46 (12.01%) were female. The most patients with respiratory failure were 67 (17.49%) in the age group of 51-60 years and at least 71 years (71%) were registered in the 15-year-old group (3.91%) (Table 1). In the arterial blood gas analysis, the average pH and p_H in men and women were 7,3 ± 2,1 SD and 7,3 ± 2,7 SD, and the mean p_H value was 7,3 ± 2,5 SD. The mean values of PaCO₂ and PaO₂ were 55.0 mmHg + 7.4 SD and 60.8 mmHg + 6.8 SD, respectively. The mean level of HCO₃ was recorded as 28.4 mmol / L + 1.4 SD (Table 2).

Table 1: Age and Gender wise distribution of patients with and without Respiratory failure in Acute Exacerbation of COPD

Ages (years)	Respiratory failure	
	Yes	No
	Male	Female
40-50	15(3.92%)	13(3.40%)
51-60	45(11.75%)	22(5.74%)
61-70	20(5.22%)	6(1.57%)
71-80	10(2.61%)	5(1.30%)
Total	90(23.50%)	46(12.01%)
Grand Total	136 (35.51%)	247 (64.49%)

Table 2: Arterial blood gas Analysis of patients with Acute Exacerbation of COPD

Sex	Mean ± Standard deviation			
	pH	PaCO ₂ (mmHg)	PaO ₂ (mmHg)	HCO ₃ (mmol/L)
Male	7.3 ± 2.1	54.1 ± 7.6	59.9 ± 6.0	28.4 ± 1.3
Female	7.3 ± 2.7	56.2 ± 7.4	62.0 ± 8.0	28.4 ± 1.6
Total	7.3 ± 2.5	55.0 ± 7.4	60.8 ± 6.8	28.4 ± 1.4

Table 3: Stratification of the total study population and percentages of each age group

Ages in Years	Respiratory Failure Patients	Percentages
40-50	28	7.32%
51-60	67	17.49%
61-70	26	6.79%
71-80	15	3.91%
Total	136	35.51%

DISCUSSION:

COPD is the major cause of mortality worldwide, increasing mortality to complications such as respiratory failure and is a major socioeconomic burden. The Natural history of COPD is defined as progressively decrease in pulmonary ventilation perfusion ratio and recurrent attacks. This assisted ventilation may result in respiratory failure, which must be admitted in the ICU.

Our study was the first to determine in patients the frequency of respiratory insufficiency with acute exacerbation of COPD in our country. In our study patients with acute exacerbations have decrease respiratory function was 35.51% in frequency blood gas analysis. The frequency of respiratory insufficiency in our study is comparable to international literature. In an Indian study, presentation ABG analysis laboratory abnormalities Respiratory failure was detected in 33.8% of patients. Blood gas analysis in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, four hospitals in China during acute attack, respiratory failure, multicenter retrospective study as 46.5% of patients. Other studies have reported a frequency of respiratory failure between 16% and 35% in the literature. Generally 35% mortality 43% 23. Corrado et al. reported acute, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with chronic respiratory failure is 12.5% of patients with acute exacerbation. 20% of patients with COPD exacerbations had chronic respiratory failure type 2 in Chinese elderly

patients. In our study, the ratio was dominated by a male, ie 67,10% male: 1 male similar area was shown in other studies in international literature. In India's study, there were 87.9% of male patients with acute exacerbations of COPD. Another study had men 20,80.7%. The rate of male sovereignty in our study is related to cigarette prevalence in our society. Smoking is more common in men, with an increase in the incidence of COPD than in women due to the reason that the male patient is referred with acute exacerbation of COPD.

In our study, the patients mean age was 59.3 yrs ± 10.76 SD; The mean age of the patients was 70 years ± 8.0 years SD 20 and 62.1 years ± 9.8 SD. In China, the average age was reported as 73.4 years. Advanced age is the prognostic factor of in-hospital mortality as described by some parents.

In the arterial gas analysis, the mean pH value was 7.3 ± 2.5 SD. Non-invasive respiratory support should be considered in patients with severe acidosis (pH <7.26) and / or increased partial pressure of arterial CO2, non-supporting support, and controlled oxygen. A pH higher than 7.26 is a better predictor of survival over an acute period.

Due to the absence of health facilities, most COPD patients remain undiagnosed in our territory and diagnosed in advanced stages of COPD. The JPMC is a tertiary care hospital and patients are referred from distant areas of the state where health facilities are inadequate. Most patients with acute exacerbations are not properly

managed at the periphery and cause this condition to deteriorate. The main cause of respiratory failure is high frequency in our study.

In our study, respiratory insufficiency was not classified as acute or chronic respiratory failure, which is an important constraint in our study. This is a focused work, so the result can not be generalized, but because there is no good evidence that respiratory failure is very common in our setting in acute exacerbations of COPD. Broad multi-center studies should be done to confirm these findings.

CONCLUSION:

This study has shown that respiratory failure is very common in patients presenting with acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. This finding indicates the presence of a very important health problem and is an important complication of acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Because of the high prevalence of COPD in our country, it is important in terms of morbidity and mortality. It also demonstrates that measures must be taken to organize the facilities for the management of the promised patients. In tertiary care patients receiving a large number of patients with respiratory insufficiency, facilities such as controlled oxygen therapy, NIPPV, mechanical ventilation and specialist staff trained in the treatment of these patients and respiratory intensive care must be available. This will help to reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with the condition.

Considering the impact of COPD on health care resources, it is essential to prevent effective COPD exacerbations and to develop effective strategies to quit smoking.

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